

STUDIES IN THE COTARNINE SERIES. PART VIII. DERIVATIVES OF 1-AMINOMETHYLHYDROCOTARNINE.

BY B. B. DEY AND (MISS) P. LAKSHMI KANTAM.

The physiological action of some aminomethylhydrocotarnine derivatives has recently been studied by Magidson and Gorbowizki (*Ber.*, 1935, 66, 656) who report that the compounds have strong mydriatic action. An investigation of the reaction between anhydrocotarninomethylamine and several nitro-aromatic acid chlorides, *e.g.*, *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride and the reduction of the resulting compounds was undertaken in the hope that these products, on account of their analogy in structure to certain well known synthetic drugs like novocaine, etc., should develop important medicinal properties.

The observation of Magidson and his co-worker (*loc. cit.*) on the reduction of anhydrocotarninonitromethane by means of stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid to the methylamino compound as a pale yellow solid, m.p. 183°, could not be confirmed; the amine was always obtained as a yellow oil, an yield of 62% being realised by using zinc dust and alcoholic sodium hydroxide as a reducing agent (*cf.* Haworth and Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1444).

The amine reacts at once with benzoyl chloride, *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride, acetyl chloride, etc., in benzene solution, the hydrochloride separating out in quantitative yield. The free bases were prepared from the hydrochlorides by treating with strong ammonia for a long time. The reduction of the *p*-nitrobenzoylaminoethylhydrocotarnine into the amino compound was effected by shaking with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid. The products which crystallised well from absolute alcohol were strong bases easily soluble in cold dilute acids to neutral solutions.

A detailed study of the pharmacological actions of these derivatives is being carried out in the Medical College, Madras.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Anhydrocotarninonitromethane (Hope and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 101, 2114), crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms melting at 129°. The yield is quantitative. It forms a sparingly soluble hydrochloride (m.p. 189°) with the colour changing to yellow at 150°, and a picrate (m.p. 136-37°).

Anhydrocotarninomethylamine (Haworth and Perkin, *loc. cit.*; Magidson and Gorbowizki, *loc. cit.*) was obtained by the reduction of anhydrocotarninonitromethane (5 g.) with zinc and sodium hydroxide in methyl alcoholic solution and working up in the usual way. It was obtained as a pale yellow oil (3.1 g.) which decomposed on distillation. The dihydrochloride was precipitated on saturating the ethereal solution of the base with dry hydrogen chloride. It is readily soluble in water and alcohol, m. p. 227°. It formed a *picrate* (m.p. 200°) and a sparingly soluble *sulphate* (m.p. 220°).

Benzoylaminomethylhydrocotarnine.—To the benzene solution of anhydrocotarninomethylamine, the required amount of benzoyl chloride was added with stirring. There was a vigorous reaction with evolution of heat and the hydrochloride of the benzoyl derivative quickly separated out. The solid was filtered after some time, washed well with dry benzene and the crude *hydrochloride* crystallised from hot water as colourless, hard, prismatic needles, m.p. 238-40°. The free base was liberated by keeping the hydrochloride in contact with strong ammonia. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless thick rhombic plates, m.p. 125°. (Found: C, 67.3; H, 5.99; N, 7.99. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires C, 67.79; H, 6.22; N, 7.91 per cent). The *picrate* crystallised from rectified spirit in short needles, m.p. 175-77°.

Action of Methyl Iodide on Anhydrocotarninomethylamine.

The amine was treated with excess of methyl iodide, when the reaction was instantaneous. The product was left overnight with some more of methyl iodide. The excess of methyl iodide was removed in vacuum and the solid was treated with cold water which dissolved most of it leaving a small amount of a thick oil. The clear yellow solution was evaporated in vacuum when the methiodide was obtained as a pale yellow crystalline hygroscopic solid, m.p. 135° (decomp.). (Found : I, 42.66. $C_{17}H_{28}O_3N_2I_2$, $2H_2O$ requires I, 42.45 per cent).

Acetylaminomethylhydrocotarnine.—The amine was treated with the required amount of acetyl chloride. The hydrochloride which separated in a crystalline state soon changed into an oily mass as it was very hygroscopic and absorbed moisture. It was dissolved in water and the yellow solution basified with caustic soda. The thick oil, which separated, solidified on washing with aqueous alcohol. It crystallised from 50% alcohol in colourless thin plates soluble in ether, m.p. 141° . (Found : N, 9.1. $C_{15}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.58 per cent).

p-Nitrobenzoylaminomethylhydrocotarnine.—*p*-Nitrobenzoyl chloride (2.6 g.), dissolved in benzene (10 c.c.), was slowly added to a solution of anhydrocotarninomethylamine (3.5 g.) in dry benzene (10 c.c.). The hydrochloride of the base separated almost immediately as yellow crystals. The crude hydrochloride, after washing with benzene and then with water and drying, weighed 4.5 g. The hydrochloride is practically insoluble in cold water but crystallises from boiling water in colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 234° . [Found : H_2O (at $110^{\circ}/5mm.$) 4.35. $C_{20}H_{21}O_6N_3$, HCl, H_2O requires H_2O , 3.97 per cent. Found : Cl (dried salt), 7.39. $C_{20}H_{21}O_6N_3$, HCl requires Cl, 8.14 per cent].

The free base was obtained from the powdered hydrochloride by keeping it in contact with strong ammonia for 24 hours. The solid changed at first into a sticky mass which slowly became granular. It was filtered, washed well with water and crystallised from hot rectified spirit as light yellow rhombic plates, m.p. 138° , yield 3.1 g. from 3.8 g. of the hydrochloride. (Found : N, 10.71. $C_{20}H_{21}O_6N_3$ requires N, 10.52 per cent). It formed a sparingly soluble *nitrate* (fern shaped crystals), m.p. 190° , and a *picrate*, m.p. 138° .

p-Aminobenzoylaminomethylhydrocotarnine.—The foregoing nitro-compound (2.5 g.) was powdered and gradually added to a mixture of stannous chloride (9 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.) and a small piece of granulated tin and the whole shaken in a mechanical shaker for about 10 hours. Water (125 c.c.) was added, the clear liquid was basified

with excess of 25% sodium hydroxide and the separated solid washed with water, dried on a porous plate and then in the desiccator and the dry solid extracted repeatedly either with warm benzene or absolute alcohol (60°). The amino-compound separated from the hot solvent in colourless, short prismatic rods, m.p. 185°. It dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid to a clear solution and was reprecipitated unchanged on basification, yield 1.2 g. It formed a *picrate*, m.p. 167°, and a red dye when diazotised and coupled with β -naphthol. (Found : C, 64.89; H, 6.23; N, 11.09. $C_{20}H_{23}O_4N_3$ requires C, 65.04; H, 6.23; N, 11.39 per cent). The *acetyl* derivative separated from dilute alcohol in rectangular plates, m.p. 135°.

m-Nitrobenzoylaminoethylhydrocotarnine was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from rectified spirit in light yellow rhombic plates, m.p. 95°. (Found : N, 10.56. $C_{20}H_{21}O_6N_3$ requires N, 10.52 per cent). The sparingly soluble *hydrochloride* crystallised from hot water containing a drop of hydrochloric acid in yellow, diamond-shaped plates, m.p. 185°. It formed a *picrate*, m.p. 196-98°.

m-Aminobenzoylaminoethylhydrocotarnine.—The reduction of the *m*-nitro-compound to the amino body was effected as in the other case with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow thin plates, m.p. 80°. It dissolves readily in cold dilute acids and is recovered unchanged on basification. (Found : N, 11.81. $C_{20}H_{23}O_4N_3$ requires N, 11.38 per cent). On diazotising its solution in cold hydrochloric acid and coupling with β -naphthol, a deep red dyestuff was thrown down.

o-Nitrobenzoylaminoethylhydrocotarnine was prepared from anhydrocotarninomethylamine and *o*-nitrobenzoyl chloride. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 143-45°. (Found : N, 10.88. $C_{20}H_{21}O_6N_3$ requires N, 10.52 per cent). The *hydrochloride* crystallised in short rectangular rods, m.p. 240° (decomp.). The *picrate* crystallised in prisms, m.p. 165°.

o-Aminobenzoylaminoethylhydrocotarnine was obtained as an oil by the reduction of the nitro-compound in the usual way. The *picrate* crystallised from methyl alcohol in rectangular plates, m.p. 175°. Diazotisation and coupling with β -naphthol gave a deep red dyestuff.